

USING WEB2 TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Rapid advancement of technology in our modern life has made it possible to improve interaction between teacher and student exposing them to a lesson where main objectives can be maximized by achievements of web tools, especially, web2. In this thesis, particular aim is directed towards defining the role of them in teaching English language effectively from the perspective of Uzbekistan that has recently become a core topic area of research in our country. It mainly tries to discuss and draw final conclusions on effective implementation of web2 tools among secondary school pupils.

Key words: *interaction, collaboration, knowledge sharing, movenote, prezi, emaze.*

Human evolution with regards to reaching maturity has passed many steps such as in learning another language, and almost in any period one has been inclined to adapt oneself to the very best condition suitable to make them progress. For this reason, scientists have always been in search of the most effective methods, materials or tools available to apply to increase literacy of population in terms of language acquisition. Current success of web2 tools is no exception in this sense as they are modern trends in every aspect of our life that helps to boost both young ambitious youth and old generation's drive for learning foreign language.

Likewise, web2 tools have occupied nowadays the role of major language educator both for its popularity and efficiency due to several reasons as having opportunity to have access at any time and with no reliance upon the teacher solely when you are provided with the privilege of e-learning. Taking into consideration all of these points, this paper, firstly, deals with the discussion of defining basic terminology of web2 tools in teaching foreign language. In a matter of fact, the study of web2 tools in teaching foreign languages can offer various sources and information to have a better sight on its meaning, the role it plays in current educational purposes. For this reason, it is important for language teachers to be aware of the latest and best

equipment and to have a full knowledge of what is available in any given situation. Teachers can use Multimedia Technology, in our case, web2 tools to give more colorful, stimulating lectures (new Horizons). The teaching principle should be to appreciate new technologies in the areas and functions where they provide something decisively new useful and never let machines takeover the role of the teacher or limit functions where more traditional ways are superior. There are various reasons why all language learners and teachers must know how to make use of the new technology. Here we also need to emphasize that the new technologies develop and disseminate so quickly that we cannot avoid their attraction and influence in any form.

Majority of people have been active users of the tools that are called web2. Though there is no final exact definition on what exactly web2 is, the term is clearly linked with a second generation of World Wide Web, making it possible for people to cooperate and share information online easier. Actually there are many definitions in the literature defining what web2 is. However, the definitions can display an extensive variety depending on how you approach web2. Web2 is "a Web technology that aims to enhance creativity, information sharing and collaboration among users". The key words in this definition *creativity, information sharing and collaboration* actually represent how they can be used in education, in this case, English language teaching.

Materials used in traditional classrooms are mostly static text based materials. These include main course books, workbooks, lecture notes and handouts. All these materials are to a great extent static in essence and language teachers have the responsibility of bringing interactivity and dynamism into their teaching environments. However, the use of web2 tools can add interactivity to language teaching and learning environments and materials used in these environments. There have been many studies conducted to explore the use of web2 tools in language teaching settings. The number of these studies is continuously increasing since educators and scholars have been seeking to investigate different aspects of web2 tools. However, there is absolutely a need for experimental studies to investigate the use of web2 tools in language teaching in terms of many aspects.

In response to this need, this study has aimed to explore the necessity of integrating web2 tools in teaching English language in secondary education system of Uzbekistan as it has been flourishing and gaining more attention by state standards over the past few years. This can be cited by the fact that on May 6, 2021 the president of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev¹, held a video conference the topic of which was dedicated to the problems of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan. He pointed out that "It is time to establish a new system of foreign language teaching in our country,

which will be a solid foundation for the future. As long as we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on school, high school, college and university graduates must be fluent in at least 2 foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion of the activity of the head of each educational institution,”.

As it is noted above current language teaching policy in Uzbekistan paves the way for highly advanced future for teaching English language, mainly. It is worth mentioning this presents new opportunities to the teachers of English language to seek out latest approachable ways. In this study, the researcher takes into consideration this fact deeply realizing the fact that new solutions are to appear in teaching reforms. Although web2 tools is almost on the way of being well-known teaching tools they still need to be investigated thoroughly in the perspective of our national language teaching system.

The actuality of the paper can be stressed by its significance in present language teaching environment which has made possible to apply any innovations in the sphere of technology in language classes. Despite the fact that modern technologies and applications of web2 tools are already well in use in English language classes currently there has not been created an accurate guidance of instructions on how to apply them effectively for different age groups, in particular, for secondary school pupils. That's why this thesis intends to create the model of teaching through working out and finding the best educational web2 tools to improve foreign language learning condition of pupils. This emphasizes significance of the study that mainly concentrates on analyzing useful web2 tools as blogs, wikis, podcasts and etc. in teaching English language more effectively. Additionally, it will in itself create an opportunity for the teachers to reveal key points in making more entertaining lessons avoiding from previously applied methods of teaching where learners had less exposure to IT sources becoming too reliant on worksheets or task-based exercises.

The novelty of the research is determined by the fact that web2 tools have been acknowledged as one of the most approachable innovations in world language teaching policy. However, it has been studied less in the perspective of Uzbekistan to which the researcher has almost been unable to find data to compare it with foreign scientists' researches. Therefore, all presented investigation in this paper can be accepted as another important step forward in offering new chance for future language teaching system in Uzbekistan where tendency for using web2 tools in classes has been increasing to maximize all available opportunities in educating future generation competitive. Here, it is worth mentioning some latest web2 tools applicable in secondary education system to make teaching better.

Web 2.0 technologies which are mostly used users include: blogs, Wikis, YouTube, social bookmarking, podcasts, webcasts, Facebook, My space, Flickr, Twitter, Skype, and Second Life. New tools that integrate image, video and text in different formats along with providing zooming presentations and strong 3D online templates have become some of the new tools used. Some of these tools include Movenote, Prezi, and Emaze.

Movenote is one excellent tool for enhancing teaching English and learning experience. With this tool the learners can create video presentations online and on mobile devices. It is an excellent tool for providing a flipped classroom approach. In addition, secondary school pupils are able to present online and present content that will be open for sharing towards relaxed and different atmosphere. Recording the presentations is very easy and Google drive along with other virtual disks can help store the content.

Prezi is well known by teachers as the zoomable presentation tool. It creates dynamic presentations thanks in part to the tools it provides. An individual is able to download his power point presentations, create content and integrate video, audio, and text. The lesson could be completely mapped by class, unit, or share it in a web site or interactive white board. The zooming aspect provides a tridimensional easy to use format that pupils could use in order to present.

On the other hand *Emaze* brings interactive presentations to another level. This multiplatform provides the teacher and the learner with plenty of tools to show their technology and content skills. It's very simple to use by only selecting the template and start working. The aspect of sharing is very simple and no pluggings are necessary, by this means that runs on any device. This gives the teacher and learner great flexibility. The teacher or the learner could import ppt presentations. The tool has a liability that could become an asset for the learner. It's that the free account publishes everything public. This opens the door for the teacher and the learner to create together and produce process writing so that the final and saved presentation is perfect.

Web2 tools are arriving to enhance the English classroom. They provide the necessary strength and reliability to let the learners achieve fluency and the teacher to create different scenarios for learning. Every instructor needs to know the importance with the use of blogs, wikis, and podcasts. In addition, by connecting web2 and learning English to the curriculum will develop the necessary connections between the TESOL technology standards and the English language teachers and learners. All in all, it's important to consider that new trends like Gamification and Game Based Learning are getting stronger and more convenient for the ESL learner in his quest for achieving fluency. These strategies could be implemented together with the use of the web2.

Additionally, technology can only become effective and useful in language teaching and learning environments in hands of competent teachers. When it comes considering the use of web2 in language education, teachers should first decide whether these tools serve to achieve objectives of the language lesson and whether they meet the pedagogical needs of teaching situation. If these two criteria are taken seriously into consideration, web2 tools can aid to create a more communicative and collaborative language teaching and learning environment.

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